

The role and importance of management of financial resources in the enterprise

G'olibjon Kuvvatov

Toshkent moliya instituti Buxgalteriya kafedresi v.v.b., dotsenti PhD

ORCID:

DOI:

Key words

financial resources, financial potential, management, monetary resources, financial relations, financial system

Annotation

In the article, the author presents the concept of financial resources of the enterprise. The goals and main tasks in the field of financial resources management are considered.

Introduction.

Financial management of an enterprise is one of the most important tasks facing any business, regardless of its form of ownership, scope, and scale of activity. The importance of this direction is due to the special role of finance, which is the only type of resources that can be transformed into any other type of resources - buildings, technologies, raw materials, and personnel. The efficiency and rationality of such a transformation largely determine the economic well-being of the enterprise, as well as all subjects interested in its development - owners, managers, creditors, the state, society, etc. Financial resources can also be used as independently operating assets that generate various types of income. Thus, the study of the basics of managing the financial resources of an enterprise in the modern economic situation is necessary for any manager, individual entrepreneur, owner, and businessman.

Research Methodology.

Economic and mathematical methods can help study the connections and influences between objects and phenomena, determine the homogeneous features in aggregates of objects and data, create models of behavior of individual enterprises based on the influence of various factors, and determine

the development trends for forecasting. Therefore, using economic and mathematical methods is the key to the accurate and detailed assessment of the financial sustainability of the enterprise, which provides the basis for optimizing managerial decisions and achieving the planned level of financial state. Thus, the financial sustainability of the enterprise is a key feature of its financial status and strategic development. Timely analysis of financial sustainability creates new opportunities for the enterprise to identify reserves to enhance its competitive position, increase market share and fulfill other tactical and strategic goals.

Literature review.

In modern market economy conditions, there is a fairly high level of competition. Each company strives to gain a foothold in the market and to function stably and efficiently. In our mind, The results of its activities are largely determined by what financial resources this business entity has, how optimal its structure is, and how they are expediently transformed into fixed and revolving funds. In this regard, effective management of financial resources is one of the most important functions of financial management, aimed at ensuring the achievement of high final results of the enterprise's economic activity. Such local

scientists as the A.A.Shomirov believe that strategic and tactical planning is important in managing the financial resources of joint-stock companies [1, p. 13]. Foreign scientists such as V. V. Bocharov, V. V. Kovalev, M. V. Romanovsky, V. M. Rodionova, and V. A. Slepov were engaged in forming and using financial resources—also, I.A.Blank, M.D.Bilyk, A.D.Vasilik, L. A. Ligonenko, V. M. Oparin, G. Donaldson, J. S. worked on the study of the problems of the functioning of financial resources of enterprises. Mill, G. Brayley, Y. Brigham, S. Myers, et al. [2, p. 103].

Analysis and results. It should be noted that there still needs to be a unified approach to determining the essence of financial resources in recent years. This is due to the differences in the views of different scientists on this problem, as well as the complexity of the economic category «financial resources.» The financial resources of an enterprise can be characterized from different points of view, for example, as a quantitative characteristic of the financial result of its activities [3, p. 25], the aggregate of funds for financial activities and financial transactions [4, p. 47], a part of the monetary resources owned or at the disposal of the enterprise and used by them for expanded reproduction, stimulating employees and other tasks [5, p. 20].

The generalization of scientific approaches to outlining the economic essence of financial potential makes it possible to form its vision of this interpretation, which is determined by the aggregate of resource provision (real and potentially available financial resources), as well as the country's capabilities (organizational, managerial, functional, infrastructural, and adaptive) for the accumulation of financial resources, their transformation into productive financial capital, its redistribution among economic actors, as well as the use of this capital to ensure balanced development of the country and its regions. This also makes it possible to substantiate that:

1. the financial system of any state is formed based on a set of parts of the finance regions, which generally constitute the national economy. At the same time, the functionality of financial relations manifests itself both within one country and outside its borders in relations with other countries of the global economy;

2. there is a close interaction between the categories of the financial potential of the region and international financial and intermediary finances;

3. the financial potential is determined by a coherent structure consisting of public

finances, local government finances, financial enterprises, and the population's finances. Thus, the financial potential of the country depends directly on the capabilities of each of its components.

It should be noted that in the aggregate, they constitute the resource base for the formation of the country's financial potential while preserving the specific features of their filling, based on the current legislation of Ukraine on the issues of the formation, distribution, and redistribution of financial resources of the state.

Considering that each participant in the process of forming financial resources is simultaneously a participant in financial relations beyond its limits, it should be assumed that only a part of their financial resources will direct to ensure the region's socio-economic development. The abovementioned fact determines the necessity of studying the resource capabilities of each of the sources of filling the financial potential based on the following starting positions, in particular:

1. belonging to the country's economy, that is, all actors involved in the creation of the financial potential of the country must be registered, located, or residing in its

territory;

2. structure-forming elements of the grouping of sources of the formation of the financial potential of the country adopted common legal requirements for them concerning the formation and distribution of financial resources;

3. The country's financial strength depends on the effectiveness of the participants' financial and economic activities in forming financial potential.

At the same time, the capacity of economic entities depends to a large extent on the financial strength of the country.

Nowadays, when the financial potential of the country's regions is formed at the expense of budget funds and with the state, private businesses and the population appear to be business entities. In addition, a significant number of sources for the formation of financial resources, their relative separation, and the chaos of movement and interaction predetermine the diverse nature of market economy subjects.

Thus, the research confirms that the static concept of «financial resources» is gradually transformed into a dynamic concept of «financial potential,» for the formation and rational use of which it is expedient to plan the movement of financial resources, regardless of their origin, including

private owners, who also seek to receive the largest profit with the lowest risk.

In a generalized form, the financial potential of a country (region) by sources of its origin is divided into the financial potential of external and internal origin.

Thus, the financial potential of external origin includes subventions and subsidies from the state budget, funds that were

needs (Figure 1).

Therefore, an enterprise's financial resources are an organization's funds and external incomes that can be used to form fixed and current assets required for the business and extended product support. Figure 1 gives a more specific definition of the nature of financial resources in the enterprise by structuring the financial resources in the

Figure 1. Sources of the financial potential [11, page 94-97]

attracted or borrowed by economic entities and people from sources external to the region, and assistance from foreign sources. The financial potential of internal origin is formed primarily through the funds of local budgets, non-budget funds, enterprises, and organizations of the region of all forms of ownership and various spheres of activity, as well as money of the population, that is, the funds that are domestic for this region. Priority in determining sources that form the financial potential is their territorial affiliation, within which money accumulation of revenues is created; as we have already noticed, business entities and the population, as a result of their production and economic activity, attracted funds from the parties focusing on appropriate funds to ensure the continuity of extended reproduction and satisfaction of other social

enterprise. The structure is based on scientific literature systematization (Figure 2).

As it supports companies in many ways, this department is a crucial and critical area. Considering the importance of financial management functions in organizations, there is always a steady demand for professionals with these skills. Today, it is possible for even non-finance professionals and people in business to learn finance concepts through a certified financial analyst course.

What are the major roles of financial management?

1. Financial Decisions and control
2. Financial planning
3. Capital management
4. Allocation and utilization of financial resources
5. Cash flow management

Figure 2. Composition of an enterprise's financial resources [6, p.3]

6. Disposal of surplus
7. Financial reporting
8. Risk Management [7, p.3]

The management of enterprises, to achieve the development tasks set in the enterprise's business plan for the current, medium-term, and long-term prospects, affects the enterprise's internal and external financial relations and the types of financial resources corresponding to them through special techniques and methods. Financial resources are monetary funds that include the income accumulated by the owners of the enterprise, as well as funds received from the outside in the form of loans» [8, p.96]. Thus, the financial resources of the enterprise consist of its own and attracted (credit) funds. The main purpose of financial resources is to ensure the solvency of the enterprise and its financial stability. At the same time, the current solvency is an external manifestation of the financial condition. The internal manifestation is financial stability, which can ensure the stability of the enterprise for a long time and the prospect of balancing various cash flows. In order to ensure the stability of the financial condition of an economic entity, it is necessary to properly coordinate the work of all departments and a rational financial resource management system.

Financial management of an enterprise, like any management system, includes an

object and a subject, i.e., a managed and managing subsystem (Figure 3)

Management of the financial resources of an enterprise is a system of principles and methods for developing and implementing management decisions related to ensuring the effectiveness of the processes of formation, distribution, and use of financial resources [10, p.45]. The purpose of managing the financial resources of the enterprise is to ensure effective financing of its development, both in the current period and in the future, in all areas of activity, including compliance with financial legislation, maximizing the welfare of the owners of the enterprise, timeliness, and completeness of settlements with all parts of the financial system. Following this goal, the following can be distinguished as the main tasks of managing the financial resources of the enterprise:

1. ensuring an uninterrupted process of formation of financial resources for solving the tasks of the development of the enterprise of a tactical and strategic nature;
2. optimization of the structure of sources of formation of financial resources of the enterprise to minimize the cost of borrowed capital;
3. optimal distribution of financial resources in the main areas of the enterprise;
4. minimizing the level of risk in the process of managing the financial resources

of the enterprise;

5. development of a mechanism for rapid changes in the structure of the financial resources of the enterprise and the directions of their use following changing conditions;

6. creation of an effective system of control over the formation and use of financial resources of the enterprise;

7. the study of foreign experience in managing the financial resources of the enterprise;

8. introduction of new methods of

methods is the key to an accurate and detailed assessment of the financial sustainability of the enterprise, which provides the basis for optimizing managerial decisions and achieving the planned level of financial state. Thus, the financial sustainability of the enterprise is a key feature of its financial status and strategic development. Timely analysis of financial sustainability creates new opportunities for the enterprise to identify reserves to enhance its competitive position, increase market share and fulfill other tactical and strategic goals.

Managing subsystem (subject) of financial management

Organizational structure of financial management (main services, personnel)

Financial tools (methods, models)

Information base of the company's finances

Technical means of financial management

Managed subsystem (object) of financial management

Financial relations:

1. with suppliers and buyers;
2. with budgets of all levels;
3. with the owners;
4. with the employees of the enterprise;
5. with financial institutions (banks, insurance companies, etc.)

Financial resources:

1. fixed assets;
2. intangible assets;
3. inventories;
4. accounts receivable;
5. monetary assets

Sources of financial resources:

1. equity (funds of shareholders and founders);
2. borrowed funds;
3. accounts payable

Figure 3. Structure of the financial management system of the enterprise [9, p.10]

managing financial resources;

9. formation of optimal conditions for attracting foreign capital; - improving the level of training of managerial personnel;

10. analysis of the financial and economic indicators of the enterprise and evaluation of the effectiveness of its management personnel based on the results.

Economic and mathematical methods can help study the connections and influences between objects and phenomena, determine the homogeneous features in aggregates of objects and data, create models of behavior of individual enterprises based on the influence of various factors, and determine the development trends for forecasting. Therefore, using economic and mathematical

For the effective functioning of the financial management system of the enterprise and the rational impact of the management system on the managed one, it is necessary to use a modern financial management methodology based on certain principles.

The basic general principles of management were developed in the last century by the French scientist Henri Fayol. Financial management, being a part of the general management of the enterprise, on the one hand, is based on universal management principles, the most important of which are:

1. The principle of economic efficiency. In any company, the financial management

system assumes expenses (costs), which should always strive to a minimum and be covered by certain revenues (sales revenue).

2. Focus on strategic development goals. If, for example, the company is focused on business growth or diversification, then it would be reasonable to increase the number of borrowed types of funds as part of the sources of funds. A strategy of limited growth or reduction requires reducing risks, and therefore, it is necessary to focus more on equity and strive to reduce fixed costs.

3. High dynamism of management (flexibility). Any financial manager should react very quickly to changes in the external environment (politics, economy, market conditions) and apply appropriate methods and models of financial management.

4. Alternative. Since financial decisions are often made in conditions of risk and uncertainty, it is essential to use multivariate approaches to assess the situation (when developing business plans and in operational and financial management).

5. Optimization of the main financial indicators. When managing the finances of an enterprise, adopting a particular management decision can lead to opposite effects in various fields of activity.

Thus, implementing high-yield financial investments can cause a deficit in financing production activities, a sharp increase in profitability can lead to decreased liquidity indicators, etc.

On the other hand, considering the

finances of an enterprise and its management as a special type of activity, A.I.Samylin also identifies several important principles:

1. publicity, i.e., the availability and openness of information about the company's activities (except for confidential information), the public's interest in the goals, objectives, and decisions of the company;

2. the scale, significant impact on the geographical market of goods, and the versatility of activities;

3. consolidation of financial statements, formation of general statements of the enterprise (very often, the structure of large companies includes various subsidiaries that conduct independent activities), etc.

Conclusion. Thus, the concept of financial resources is an essential category in the implementation of the activities of any enterprise. Financial resources are constantly in motion; their distinctive features from other resources are the monetary form of existence, belonging to a specific entity, effective use for profit, and economic growth of the organization. Taking care of financial stability and stability, it is essential for an organization to effectively manage its financial resources, correctly distributing them by type of activity and over time. Effective financial management allows the company to remain stable, solvent, and therefore stable functioning and competitive in the markets. Moreover, all this, in turn, makes it possible for an economic entity to outline its economic development for the long term.

References

1. A.A.Shomirov "Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlar moliyaviy resurslarini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari" dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati 24-bet.
2. Остапенко Л.М. Эволюция понятия «финансовые ресурсы» и современные подходы к определению // Вестник современной науки. 2016. - № 1- С.101-104
3. Финансы, денежное обращение и кредит: Учебник / Под ред. Г.Б.Поляка. - 3-е изд., перераб. и доп. - М.: Юнити-Дана, 2009. - 639 с.
4. Барулин С.В. Финансы: учебник. -2-е изд., стер. - М.: Кнорус, 2011.- 640 с.
5. Podablonskaya L. M. Finance: a textbook for university students. - Moscow: Unity-Dana, 2010. - 407 p.
6. Makka Alaudinovna Khamatkhanova. Approaches to the generation of an enterprise's financial resources in the context of their limitation. Vol. 39 (Number 18) Year 2018 · Page 22
7. <https://talentedge.com/articles/role-financial-management-organization>
8. Агарков А.П. Экономика и управление на предприятии / А.П. Агарков [и др.]. - М.: Дашков и К, 2013. - 400 с.
9. Управление финансовыми ресурсами предприятия : учеб. пособие / Н.Л.Савченко; М-во науки и высш. образования Рос. Федерации, Урал. федер. ун-т. - Екатеринбург : Изд-во Урал. ун-та, 2019. -164 с.
10. Бланк И.А. Управление финансовыми ресурсами.-М.: Омега - Л: ООО «Эльга», 2011. - 768 с.
11. Kateryna Indus The role and place of financial resources for the development of regions. Baltic Journal of Economic Studies June 2018. Page 94-97